

Catching up? Sex differences in prior conceptual knowledge, socio-emotional experiences, and academic achievements among STEM undergraduates

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Sex differences
STEM education
Prior knowledge
Socio-emotional factors
University education

ABSTRACT

The present study examined sex differences in prior conceptual knowledge, socio-emotional factors, self-regulated learning, and grade point average (GPA) among first-year students in mathematics-intensive STEM programs ($n = 2074$, 342 female). At entry to university, women scored lower than men on tests of conceptual knowledge in math ($d = -0.51$) and physics ($d = -0.88$). During their first university year, women experienced higher levels of belonging uncertainty ($d = 0.41$) and stress ($d = 0.70$). In their first-year exams, women obtained a slightly lower GPA than men ($d = -0.23$). Hierarchical multiple regressions revealed that prior conceptual knowledge and grades, followed by socio-emotional factors and self-regulation, were independently predictive of first-year GPA. The effect of sex on first-year GPA was eliminated when either of these factors or their combination were included. The sex difference in first-year GPA was small, given the initial differences in prior knowledge. We discuss processes enabling students to compensate for lower prior knowledge as well as socio-emotional costs.

Educational relevance and implications statement: In a large sample of first-year university students in mathematics-intensive STEM fields, we found that women entered university with lower prior knowledge in math and physics, reported higher belonging uncertainty and stress during their first year, and obtained lower grades at the end of their first year. Yet, the sex difference in prior knowledge was much larger than the sex difference in first-year grade point average (GPA), demonstrating that women were able to compensate. The statistical analyses help to understand the interplay of sex, relevant prior knowledge, as well as socio-emotional factors and self-regulation, for first-year university STEM students' achievement. On a practical level, our findings point towards the importance of supporting students of any sex or gender in compensating for lacks in relevant prior knowledge.

1. Introduction

While the number of women in higher STEM education has been increasing globally over time, women continue to be underrepresented in math-intensive STEM subjects such as mathematics, physics, engineering, and computer science (sometimes abbreviated as MPECS; Cheryan et al., 2017; Ceci et al., 2014; Cimpian et al., 2020; Francesconi

& Parey, 2018; Su & Rounds, 2015; Williams, 2018). According to a vast body of research from multiple disciplines, the accumulated evidence points towards a complex interplay of factors underlying sex differences in STEM interest, choice of study field, and academic success (for reviews, see Ceci & Williams, 2010; Ceci et al., 2014; Miller et al., 2015; Wang & Degol, 2017). Beliefs and stereotypes about science and mathematics (Leslie et al., 2015; Napp & Breda, 2022; Nosek et al., 2009) as

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2025.102762>

Received 28 July 2023; Received in revised form 11 July 2025; Accepted 17 July 2025

Available online 24 July 2025

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well as sex differences in academic and occupational interests (Diekman et al., 2017; Stewart-Williams & Halsey, 2021; Su et al., 2009) may explain sex differences in initial decisions on whether to enter math-intensive STEM areas or not. However, sex differences continue to exist beyond career choices: Women who have already made a choice for math-intensive STEM university programs often show lower rates of retention and academic success than men (e.g., Cimpian et al., 2020; Francesconi & Parey, 2018). To explain these differences, some authors point to sex differences in prerequisites for academic success (e.g., prior knowledge) that are already present before the start of university education (e.g., Ceci et al., 2014; Stoet & Geary, 2018), while others focus on factors (e.g., socio-emotional factors) that emerge over the course of university studies (e.g., Almukhambetova et al., 2023; Good et al., 2012).

In the present research, our overall aim was to contribute to a better understanding of factors affecting the academic success of men and women who have already opted for undergraduate studies in math-intensive STEM programs. We applied achievement tests in mathematics and physics with a special focus on the conceptual knowledge that students possess when entering university. At two additional measurement points in students' first undergraduate year, we assessed two different sets of self-reported socio-emotional and self-regulation variables. Thus, we tap into sex differences existing at the start of university education, as well as sex differences emerging over the course of students' first year. Finally, we relate these measures to students' first-year GPA.

1.1. Men and women in math-intensive university STEM programs

Sex differences exist in educational and occupational choices, in general, as well as within STEM fields. The largest difference seems to be between 'people' oriented fields, which are more often preferred by female students, and 'objects'-oriented fields, which are more often preferred by male students (Diekman et al., 2017; Su et al., 2009). Within STEM, women are equally represented or even overrepresented in life-science fields such as medicine, pharmacy, and biology, while they are underrepresented in math-intensive STEM fields (Cheryan et al., 2017; Su & Rounds, 2015; for an overview see Berkowitz et al., 2020). These differential choices are influenced by a variety of factors, including performance profiles and previous achievements (Stoet & Geary, 2018; Wang et al., 2013), socially shared stereotyped beliefs and expectations about fields (Leslie et al., 2015; Napp & Breda, 2022), as well as potentially stereotyped self-beliefs (Eccles & Wang, 2016; Marsh et al., 2021).

In addition to sex differences in career choices, there also appear to be sex differences in the academic success of those students who have already made a choice for STEM. There are several indicators of academic success, with grades (typically the grade point average, GPA) and retention (i.e., the proportion of students remaining in a chosen field until graduation) being the most frequently used indicators in quantitative analyses. Evidence regarding sex differences in GPA and retention rates during higher STEM education is mixed (e.g., Francesconi & Parey, 2018; Maries et al., 2022; Odom et al., 2021; Sonnert & Fox, 2012; Stearns et al., 2020). Achievement gaps in GPA favoring males appear to be more common in male dominated, math-intensive STEM fields such as engineering and computer science (Cheryan et al., 2017; Cimpian et al., 2020; Walton et al., 2015; Whitcomb et al., 2021), and in learning settings with large courses, traditional lectures, and exam-based grading (Odom et al., 2021). While there is no indication of a systematic underperformance of women in STEM, persistent sex-related achievement gaps are regularly observed in specific STEM courses or programs, and understanding and tackling these gaps is a declared goal of many university educators (e.g., Almukhambetova et al., 2023; Cromley et al., 2016; Farrar et al., 2023; Gayles & Ampaw, 2014). For addressing achievement gaps in undergraduate STEM performance, the first terms in university education are a critical period, as students' experiences in

their chosen program, and the feedback that they get on their performance, are important in determining their personal choice to remain in or opt out of their field (e.g., Eather et al., 2022; Murtaugh et al., 1999).

1.2. Factors affecting academic success at entry to university

The transition from school to university requires students to cope with a multitude of not only cognitive, but also social, emotional, and motivational challenges. There is a rich literature on the roles that cognitive factors, socio-emotional factors, and self-regulation play for the academic success of university students during their first year and beyond (for systematic reviews, see for example Richardson et al., 2012; Robbins et al., 2004; Schneider & Preckel, 2017; van der Zanden et al., 2018). In the following, we briefly summarize key factors that play a role in determining the academic success of first-year university STEM students.

1.2.1. Prior knowledge and achievements

Prior knowledge measured with standardized tests or indicated by school grades are among the strongest predictors of further academic success, each capturing somewhat different aspects of students' learning history (Richardson et al., 2012; Schneider & Preckel, 2017; Simon-smeyer et al., 2022). There are different types of prior knowledge, among which *conceptual knowledge* is of particular relevance to the context of STEM learning (Hofer et al., 2018; Mazur, 2015; Stern, 2017). Differently from automated procedures or memorized facts, conceptual knowledge reflects students' deeper understanding in a domain, thus facilitating transfer across time and tasks (Schneider et al., 2011). Concept inventories are widely used in science education for assessing this type of knowledge, as they capture an understanding of selective, yet fundamental subsets of knowledge that is not always reflected in school grades, exercises, or exams (Epstein, 2013; Lichtenberger et al., 2017; Madsen et al., 2013).

Individual differences in prior knowledge may be a result of multiple factors, including the amount and quality of prior learning opportunities (e.g., Hofer et al., 2018; Schneider & Preckel, 2017), individuals' general cognitive ability (e.g., Wai & Tran, 2022), as well as their interest and motivation (e.g., Eccles & Wang, 2016). While male and female students do not typically differ in their cognitive potential for learning math and science (Halpern et al., 2007; Wang & Degol, 2017), they often differ in their preferences and educational choices (e.g., Diekman et al., 2017; Eccles & Wang, 2016). In many countries, more boys than girls choose advanced math and science classes in high school (e.g., Card & Payne, 2021; Epstein, 2007; Marsh et al., 2019; Trusty, 2002). Possibly as a result of these previous academic choices and opportunities, male students have been found to have higher conceptual math and physics knowledge than female students in some samples of STEM undergraduates (e.g., Hofer & Stern, 2016; Kost et al., 2009; Madsen et al., 2013). When it comes to STEM study programs that are math-intensive, as those in focus of our study, gaps in math and physics knowledge are crucial because these subjects typically constitute a major part of students' first-year curriculum and thus play an important role for students' retention in STEM (Kopparla, 2019).

1.2.2. Socio-emotional factors and self-regulation

In addition to the cognitive demands of university-level STEM education, first-year students also face socio-emotional and motivational challenges. Students need to develop a sense of belonging in the chosen field and among their new peers (Strayhorn, 2012), they must come to terms with the stressful transition to a new context for living and learning (Maymon & Hall, 2021; Thompson et al., 2021), and they must effectively self-regulate their learning and persist even in the face of setbacks (Lin et al., 2023; Martens & Metzger, 2017).

1.2.2.1. *Developing a sense of belonging.* Newly enrolled students need to

develop new aspects of their social identity, nurture new friendships, and grow into new communities (Gale & Parker, 2014; Tinto, 1998). In this context, developing a feeling of belonging to relevant social groups (e.g., one's university department) is important for students' well-being, as well as for their persistence and academic success (e.g., Dutcher et al., 2022; Good et al., 2012; Höhne & Zander, 2019; Naylor et al., 2017). For students identifying with a minority group, such as women in male-dominated fields, developing a sense of belonging may be impaired if they feel threatened by negative stereotypes, such as stereotypes questioning female students' mathematical abilities (Walton et al., 2015). Students might then question whether they belong at the university or in the field they have chosen, and be more easily unsettled by inevitable setbacks, thus experiencing *belonging uncertainty* (Walton et al., 2015; Walton & Cohen, 2007). A high degree of belonging uncertainty will likely impede learning motivation and may lead students to change study fields or choose other career paths (Höhne & Zander, 2019). On the other hand, feeling a secure sense of belonging has been shown to be a positive predictor of retention beyond the first university year (Strayhorn, 2012; Zumbunn et al., 2014). Applied to the context of male-dominated STEM subjects, research has found that experiencing belonging uncertainty is common among female students (Binning et al., 2020; Deiglmayr et al., 2019; Master et al., 2016). Math-intensive STEM fields have been described as characterized by masculine cultures that signal a low sense of belonging to women (Cheryan et al., 2017; Murphy et al., 2007). Thus, in these fields, women might be more prone than men to experience belonging uncertainty, which in turn may hamper their academic success.

1.2.2.2. Coping with stress. During the first years in tertiary education, students' psycho-social functioning worsens, as indicated by declining self-esteem, less productive affective coping, and higher experienced depression, anxiety, and stress (Conley et al., 2020; Maymon & Hall, 2021). In many samples, female college students report higher levels of stress than male college students (Beiter et al., 2015; Graves et al., 2021; Mahmoud et al., 2012;). Stressors faced by first-year students include having to deal with negative feedback and setbacks, both academically and socially, and a lack of social support, in particular when newly arriving at university (Pluut et al., 2015). To the extent that female students in math-intensive STEM fields face a masculine, stereotype-enhancing culture (Cheryan et al., 2017), and perceive low social support and belonging (Good et al., 2012), stress may be expected to be substantially higher for females than males in these subjects (for an example, see Jensen et al., 2023). In addition, irrespective of student sex, low academic performance has been shown to increase academic stress (Stewart et al., 1999). As prior knowledge is a strong predictor of academic performance (Simonsmeier et al., 2022), low prior knowledge can be expected to increase students' academic stress by putting students at risk for low academic performance. Heightened levels of stress, on the other hand, have been shown to be linked to lower academic achievement, lower well-being, and lower retention rates (Lisnyj et al., 2023; Maymon & Hall, 2021; Pluut et al., 2015; van der Zanden et al., 2018).

1.2.2.3. Self-regulating one's learning. With the transition to university, students become responsible for their own learning to a much higher degree than they were in school (Thompson et al., 2021). Therefore, self-regulating one's learning and maintaining effort and persistence even in the face of difficulties and distractions are important abilities that tertiary students need to develop (Cohen, 2012; Higgins et al., 2023; Lin et al., 2023; Martens & Metzger, 2017). Self-regulated learning (SRL) refers to "the self-directive processes and self-beliefs that enable learners to transform their mental abilities (...) into an academic performance skill" (Zimmerman, 2008, p. 166). Models of SRL have identified different processes of SRL, representing, for example, strategies and beliefs relevant for different phases of learning activities, or drawing on

different kinds of underlying knowledge (Panadero, 2017). Volitional aspects of SRL, such as efficient time management and the avoidance of procrastination, have been found to be of particular relevance for success at university (Eckerlein et al., 2019; Kryshko et al., 2020; Richardson et al., 2012; van der Zanden et al., 2018; Wolters & Brady, 2021).

Sex differences in SRL, typically favoring females, appear to be largest during middle adolescence (Tetering et al., 2020), where they have also been shown to be related to sex differences in school achievement (Duckworth & Seligman, 2006; Weis et al., 2013). For university students, results are more mixed, with some studies reporting better SRL skills in female students at least for some SRL strategies (e.g., Baars et al., 2015; Virtanen & Nevgi, 2010), and others finding no advantage for female students (e.g., Wolters et al., 2017). SRL skills in university students have been shown to be an important predictor of academic success, regardless of sex (Eckerlein et al., 2019; Kryshko et al., 2020; Wolters et al., 2017). Relevant to our context, high SRL skills may help students catch up on gaps in prerequisites, such as prior conceptual knowledge (Cohen, 2012). Thus, self-regulated learning, in particular volitional regulation, may be particularly relevant for students with lower levels of prior knowledge, regardless of their sex. In addition, to the extent that volitional regulation differs between male and female university students, it can be expected to play a role in explaining sex differences in achievements.

1.3. The present study

The present study included first-year students at ETH Zurich, a major technological university in Switzerland, who studied in one of five math-intensive STEM bachelor degree programs: Mathematics, Physics, Computer Science, Electrical Engineering, and Mechanical Engineering. As regular reports show, female students are a minority in these study programs. At the time of data collection, the proportion of female students in the five departments ranged from 12 % (computer science) to 22 % (mathematics; Schubert & Kaczykowski-Patermann, 2017). For several years preceding our own study, administrative data had documented an achievement gap favoring male students with regards to first-year GPA and retention beyond the first year. No admission exams are required to enter a bachelor's degree program as long as students have graduated from a university-bound high school. Already upon enrollment, students choose a specific degree-program (e.g., a bachelor's in mechanical engineering). Students' curriculum during their first academic year at ETH Zurich is fixed and does not include any non-STEM courses. Rather, the first-year courses draw heavily on advanced mathematics and, with the exception of computer science, also physics. While students are enrolled in the respective departments, the specific cultures of the different departments are not yet reflected in the first-year courses. In all departments, students take mathematics courses in their first year, and for all departments, the courses and the exams in mathematics are exclusively offered by professors affiliated to the mathematics department, with a focus on genuine disciplinary concepts rather than application. Students enrolled in the mathematics and physics department undergo the same courses in their first year, which means mathematics students also have to learn physics. Students enrolled in mechanical and electrical engineering also have to undergo several courses in physics, with many of them taught by professors affiliated to the physics department. Only in computer science, physics is not a mandatory subject. Nevertheless, preliminary analyses showed that both mathematics and physics prior knowledge were predictive of first-year GPA for all students, including computer science students. Therefore, we decided to pool the data across departments. However, whenever we used students' prior knowledge in physics as a predictor, we controlled for potential bias by running the respective analysis with and without the computer science students. In all departments, reaching minimum grades in their first-year courses is highly important for students, as these grades determine whether students can continue with

their chosen program. Therefore, we treat students' first-year GPA as the main indicator of their academic success in the present study.

The main aim of our study was to identify factors that contribute to students' academic success, and in particular, factors that could help to explain sex differences in academic success. The study had three measurement points (t1, t2, and t3), but did not follow a repeated measures design. Rather, at each measurement point, indicators particularly relevant to that time point were assessed: at entry to university, prior conceptual knowledge in math and physics, high school grades and high school track, which served as our baseline predictors (t1); belonging uncertainty in mid semester (t2); and perceived stress and volitional self-regulation during exam preparation (t3). This design allowed us to examine the impact of prior knowledge and high school achievements, as well as of socio-emotional factors and self-regulation, on students' academic success during their first year in a math-intensive STEM curriculum.

In a first step, we explored sex differences in the main study variables. Based on data from earlier studies with Swiss high school students (Hofer et al., 2018; Lichtenberger et al., 2024), we had the hypothesis that female students in our sample would show lower levels of relevant conceptual prior knowledge than male students (Hypothesis 1.1). Based on the literature on barriers and biases experienced by women in STEM, we expected female students to self-report higher belonging uncertainty and higher stress during their first study year than male students (Hypothesis 1.2). Finally, based on the literature on sex-related achievement gaps in STEM, as well as on reports of the university administration for previous cohorts, we expected female students to obtain lower first-year GPAs than male students (Hypothesis 1.3). We also explored sex differences in volitional self-regulation, as this variable was hypothesized to be a relevant predictor of academic achievement. However, as the existing literature reports mixed results, no specific hypothesis was postulated.

In a second step, to better understand sources of potential differences between men and women, we examined whether sex explained variance beyond other predictors. In line with the literature on sex differences in STEM achievement, we expected that previous learning opportunities (STEM vs. non-STEM track) and achievements (high-school GPA) would explain most, if not all sex differences in students' prior conceptual knowledge in math and physics. With regards to prior knowledge, we thus tested the hypothesis that sex would not explain a significant amount of variance over and beyond track (STEM vs. non-STEM) and high-school GPA (Hypothesis 2). Based on the literature on the role of gender stereotypes and biases, we expected female students to experience higher levels of belonging uncertainty and stress than male students, even given comparable levels of prior conceptual knowledge. Therefore, we tested the hypothesis that sex would be predictive of belonging uncertainty and stress over and beyond prior knowledge and achievement (Hypothesis 3). Finally, with regards to first-year GPA, we expected that any sex differences would be partially or even fully explained by prior knowledge and achievements, socio-emotional factors, and volitional self-regulation (Hypothesis 4).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample and procedure

In two consecutive cohorts (years 2016 and 2017) in the five participating departments (Mathematics, Physics, Computer Science, Electrical Engineering, and Mechanical Engineering), university administration invited all first-year students to participate in a university teaching development project (around 3000 students). For data analysis, the data of the two cohorts were combined because the procedure and the conditions of study as well as the average students' characteristics were identical. Within each cohort, assessments were conducted at three time points (t1 – t3). The first assessment (t1) took place during the first week of the fall semester and included students'

prior conceptual knowledge in mathematics and physics. In a group setting, students were given two paper-and-pencil tests of conceptual knowledge in math and physics. The tests were administered during regular lecture sessions. Tests were announced in advance via email and in the lecture, and it was made clear that participation was voluntary, and would have no effect on course grade in any way. Students received no monetary compensation, but could check their pseudonymized test results some weeks later. To prevent potential stereotype threat (Spencer et al., 2016), students were not required to state their sex or gender on the test sheets, and no potential sex or gender differences were mentioned when introducing the tests. Rather, participants were informed that we were interested in the kinds of prior knowledge that students have upon starting at ETH Zurich. The second assessment (t2) took place in the middle of the first semester and included an online survey on students' *belonging uncertainty*. Students were invited via email, with the survey window open for three weeks. For the third assessment (t3), students were invited via email right after they had taken their first exam, with the survey window open for ten days. The first-year exams period took place either after the first or after the second semester, depending on study program and students' preference. The t3 survey included an assessment of students' *self-regulated learning* (specifically, volitional regulation), and *perceived stress*. At all three time points, other survey measures were included that were not part of the current study. Students were asked to participate in the survey to help improve teaching at ETH Zurich with no additional incentives offered. At each measurement point, students were asked for consent that their data be linked with their administrative records, for research purposes. The data obtained with the students' consent, provided in an anonymized file through the administration, was students' *high school GPA* and *high school track*, students' *first-year GPA*, as well as their *sex*. *High school GPA* is a weighted average grade based on the courses and exams students took as their graduation requirement from a university-bound, upper-track high school. It is based on grades ranging from 1 (worst) to 6 (best), with 4 being the passing grade. Thus, higher grades represent better performance. *High school track* refers to the study track that a student had selected during the last 2 or 3 years at high school. Because curricula differ between schools, it was not possible to precisely quantify the number of hours of science instruction that students had received. For our analyses, we dichotomized the profiles information into *STEM tracks* (including mathematics, natural and life sciences) and *non-STEM tracks* (all other tracks). *First-year GPA* represents a weighted average grade across a student's compulsory first-year courses. Course grades are based on final, written exams scores (i.e., not on handing in exercises or performing other tasks). For each study course, exams are composed by senior faculty members, based on standard curricula, and given collectively to the entire cohort. Each exam is graded using a scoring rubric, resulting in a raw score. Raw exam scores are transformed into grades ranging from 1 (worst) to 6 (best), with 4 being the passing grade. Thus, higher grades represent better performance. Information on students' *sex* represented the information given in the students' legal documents (i.e., sex assigned at birth, distinguishing between "male" and "female"). While legislation in many countries has come to acknowledge more than two genders, this was and still is not the case in the context in which this study was conducted. Therefore, it is possible that in a few cases, the officially assigned sex of a student may not have been aligned with their own gender identification.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Commission at ETH Zurich prior to data collection, and the study was conducted in accordance with human subjects' principles. For example, only data from students who had given informed consent to use their data for research purposes is part of this study's data set. In total, 2074 students (1732 male and 342 female) participated at least at one of the time points. The total number of students who participated in the first assessment (t1) was $N = 1545$; in the second assessment (t2) $N = 1272$ (of them, $N = 882$ participated at t1 and $N = 390$ were new); and in the third assessment $N = 992$ (of them, $N = 853$ participated either at t1 or t2, and $N = 491$

were new). The number of students by department was: Mechanical Engineering: $N = 611$ ($N = 84$ female); Computer Science: $N = 451$ ($N = 53$ female); Electrical Engineering: $N = 362$ ($N = 54$ female); Physics: $N = 348$ ($N = 74$ female); Mathematics: $N = 302$, ($N = 77$ females).

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Prior knowledge tests

In close coordination with representatives of the participating study programs, as well as the university's experts for teacher development, we selected tests covering content that was (a) relevant to courses in all participating study programs, and (b) part of the high school curriculum in Switzerland. We adapted two concept inventories, one in mathematics and one in physics, which were administered in a paper-and-pencil form, and without a strict time limit. To make the tests appropriate for large group testing, parallel versions with randomly ordered items were presented. We used the following inventories:

2.2.1.1. Mathematics. Prior conceptual math knowledge was assessed using the *Calculus Concept Inventory* (CCI) (Epstein, 2007, 2013). This test assesses conceptual understanding of basic principles of differential calculus. It consists of 11 multiple choice questions that do not involve computations. The items were translated into German by two mathematics educators, with slight modifications to the original version to adapt the tasks to the curriculum in Switzerland, and in discussion with subject matter experts from the participating departments, in order to ensure relevance for the first-year curriculum. Each correct answer was awarded one point. The maximum possible number of points was 11. Internal consistency of the test in our sample was 0.60 (Cronbach's alpha). This estimate is satisfactory for knowledge tests (Stadler et al., 2021; Taber, 2018).

2.2.1.2. Physics. Prior conceptual physics knowledge was assessed using a test of *Basic Mechanics Conceptual Understanding* (bMCU) (Hofer et al., 2017). This test assesses conceptual understanding in Newtonian mechanics. In doing so, it is similar to the concept inventory developed by Hestenes et al. (1992). However, it is specifically suitable for the secondary (i.e., high school) level. The test consists of 12 Rasch-scaled multiple choice items. Each correct answer was awarded one point, and the maximum possible number of points was 12. The bMCU was administered in its original German version. The internal consistency of the test in our sample was 0.74 (Cronbach's alpha).

2.2.2. Socio-emotional factors and self-regulation

2.2.2.1. Belonging uncertainty. *Belonging uncertainty* was assessed by the three items developed by Walton and Cohen (2007). The items were translated into German and were adapted specifically to the university under study. Participants were asked to rate the following three statements on a scale ranging from 1 (do not agree at all) to 7 (completely agree): "Sometimes I feel that I belong at ETH, and sometimes I feel that I don't belong at ETH"; "When things are going badly, I feel that maybe I don't belong at ETH"; "When something good happens, I feel that I really belong at ETH". The third item showed poor correlations with the other two items, which according to the scale's authors appears to be common (Walton & Cohen, 2007). We followed the authors recommendation and excluded the third item. With the two remaining items, internal consistency of this scale in our sample was satisfactory (Cronbach's alpha = 0.82; $r = 0.70$).

2.2.2.2. Perceived stress. Students' *perceived stress* was assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983; Cohen & Williamson, 1988). The scale is one of the most widely used measures of perceived stress among adults, including first-year university students (Maymon & Hall, 2021). The scale assesses the degree to which life situations are

perceived as unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloading. Statements are general and refer to the past month (example item: "In the last month, how often have you felt nervous and "stressed"?"). We used the 10-items scale recommended by Cohen and Williamson (1988). Statements were rated on a 5-point answering scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). Internal consistency of the test in our sample was 0.87 (Cronbach's alpha).

2.2.2.3. Volitional self-regulation. We assessed student's self-regulated learning during the exams period and therefore focused on volitional regulation strategies, which have been shown to be particularly relevant during such phases (Eckerlein et al., 2019). We employed three subscales from a German Study Motivation Questionnaire by Martens and colleagues (Martens & Metzger, 2017). These subscales assessed students' volitional regulation of learning during the post-decisional phase (Heckhausen, 1991; Martens & Metzger, 2017), which was suitable to our focus on self-regulated learning during exam preparation:

- (1) *Effort Avoidance*: 4 items assessed the dysfunctional aspect of avoiding effortful tasks (these items were reverse coded). An example item is: "Usually, I wait until shortly before the exams before I start studying, because I know it will be effortful".
- (2) *Distraction Avoidance*: 4 items assessed persistent goal pursuit by means of shielding oneself from distracting factors. An example item is: "When I study, I willfully blend out distractions".
- (3) *Persistence*: 5 items assessed persistent goal pursuit. An example item is "I will bite through, even if studying gets tough".

All items were rated on a scale ranging from 1 (completely disagree) to 4 (completely agree). Internal consistency of the scales in our sample was: persistence = 0.74, distraction avoidance = 0.79, effort avoidance = 0.90 (Cronbach's alpha).

2.3. Missing data handling

To make optimal use of the available data and minimize bias that might occur when relying on listwise deletion, we used full information maximum likelihood estimation (FIML) to account for missing data in the statistical models (e.g., Lang & Little, 2018). FIML is suitable when the data is at least missing at random (MAR), which means that missing data can be related to other measures in the data set but not to the variable on which data is missing (Enders, 2010). We included in our analyses a set of auxiliary variables (i.e., variables present in the dataset but not included in the statistical models), which is recommended for improving the precision of the FIML algorithm (Enders, 2010). The proportion of missing data per variable ranged from 18 % (for university GPA) to about 54 % on t3 variables (perceived stress and volitional regulation). More details about the proportion of missing data, correlations between missingness and the study variables, and the list of auxiliary variables are shown in Section 3 in the Supplementary Material.

2.4. Approach to data analysis

To explore sex differences in our main study variables, and to test the hypotheses regarding sex differences in prior conceptual math and physics knowledge (Hypothesis 1.1), belonging uncertainty and stress (Hypothesis 1.2), and first-year GPA (Hypothesis 1.3), we inspected mean values for male and female students. We report these differences in effect size and 95 %-confidence intervals; confidence intervals that do not include zero indicate statistically significant effects. To test our hypotheses regarding the prediction of prior conceptual knowledge (Hypothesis 2), socio-emotional factors (Hypothesis 3), and first-year GPA (Hypothesis 4), we conducted hierarchical multiple regression analyses. In these prediction models, single variables or blocks of

variables (i.e., groups of variables that are conceptually related) were added to the model in steps, enabling us to disentangle their differential effects on the dependent variables (see e.g., Marsh et al., 2019).

To investigate whether high school track and high school GPA explained sex differences in conceptual math and physics knowledge (Hypothesis 2), we conducted two hierarchical regression models for predicting scores on prior knowledge tests in physics (bMCU) and math (CCI), respectively. In each analysis, the first step was to regress the prior knowledge scores only on sex, and the second step was to add the main effects of the two high school variables (track and GPA). In order to cover the possibility that sex differences in prior knowledge might differ between STEM- and non-STEM high-school tracks, we also explored a potential interaction effect between sex and school track. The third step of the hierarchical regression thus was to include the interaction between sex and school track. To investigate whether sex indeed explained variance in socio-emotional factors beyond prior knowledge (Hypothesis 3), we regressed belonging uncertainty and perceived stress on sex (in a first step) and, additionally, on the two prior knowledge scores (in a second step). Finally, to investigate whether sex explained variance in first-year GPA beyond other variables (Hypothesis 4), we regressed first-year GPA on sex, a knowledge-achievement block (prior knowledge and high school variables), a block with the socio-emotional variables (belonging uncertainty and perceived stress), and a block with the volitional regulation variables. The rationale for using blocks of variables as predictors was to focus on the effects yielded by each block as a whole, rather than on the effects of individual variables within blocks (see e.g., Marsh et al., 2019).

To ensure that the amount of missing data is similar across model steps, all covariates were included in all model steps, so that their means and covariances with other variables were estimated. This ensured that model steps were comparable, and that differences in the estimates between steps are not due to differences in the proportion of missing data. All analyses were carried out in *Mplus* version 8.3 (Muthén & Muthén, 2017), using robust maximum likelihood estimation (MLR).

3. Results

Table 1 displays the estimated descriptive statistics for all continuous study variables split by sex (values based on observed data are reported in Table S1 in the Supplementary Material). The magnitude of sex differences is indicated by the effect size estimates in the rightmost columns. We used Cohen's d as an index of the effect size, calculated as: $d = \frac{M(\text{male}) - M(\text{female})}{\text{Pooled SD}}$. The results regarding mean sex differences are discussed in section 3.1. Regarding high school track, observed data was available for 1519 students (about 72 % of the sample). Of them, 982 (65 %) had graduated from a STEM track and 537 (35 %) from a non-

Table 1
Estimated descriptive statistics by sex, and mean sex differences.

Variable	Males (N = 1732)		Females (N = 342)		Mean difference	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	d	95 % CI
University GPA	4.55	0.74	4.38	0.73	0.23	0.10/0.36
High-school GPA	5.09	0.54	5.18	0.55	-0.16	-0.30/-0.03
bMCU	0.67	0.21	0.49	0.22	0.88	0.73/1.02
CCI	0.72	0.17	0.63	0.19	0.51	0.36/0.66
Belonging uncertainty	4.37	1.83	5.10	1.70	-0.41	-0.54/-0.27
Perceived stress	2.65	0.65	3.07	0.76	-0.62	-0.84/-0.40
Volitional regulation						
Effort avoidance	3.37	0.70	3.43	0.71	-0.08	-0.29/0.13
Distraction avoidance	2.82	0.64	2.79	0.65	0.06	-0.13/0.25
Persistence	2.75	0.57	2.65	0.67	0.17	-0.02/0.36

Note. bMCU = basic mechanics conceptual understanding; CCI = calculus concept inventory.

STEM track. Sex was not similarly distributed across high-school track: while 67.5 % ($n = 845$) of the male students came from STEM high-school tracks, only 51 % ($n = 137$) of the female students attended these tracks ($\chi^2 = 26.06, p < .001$).

The correlation matrix of the study variables is shown in Table 2 (correlations based on observed data appears in Table S2 in the Supplementary Material).

3.1. Sex differences in mean scores

As the effect size column in Table 1 indicates, there were substantial mean sex differences favoring male students on tests of prior conceptual knowledge in physics and mathematics in line with Hypothesis 1.1. Also as expected, women reported substantially higher belonging uncertainty and higher stress, in line with Hypothesis 1.2, and obtained a slightly lower GPA than males, in line with Hypothesis 1.3. These differences were statistically significant (95 %-CI does not include 0). Sex differences in reported volitional regulation of learning were negligible.

3.2. The impact of sex beyond other predictors

3.2.1. Predicting prior conceptual knowledge

As shown in Table 3, for both measures of prior conceptual knowledge (bMCU and CCI), the sex effect remained largely unchanged across all steps, with male students having higher scores than females independently of school track and high-school GPA, in contrast to Hypothesis 2. Students coming from STEM tracks had higher prior knowledge scores compared to students from other school tracks, across sexes, and accounting for high school GPA. Students with higher high school GPA also had higher prior knowledge scores compared to students with lower high school GPA, across sexes and school tracks. However, the interaction between sex and school track was not significant, implying that sex differences in prior knowledge were highly similar across school tracks (for descriptive statistics by sex and school track see Table S4 in the Supplementary Material).

3.2.2. Predicting belonging uncertainty and perceived stress

As shown in Table 4, sex had significant effects on both belonging uncertainty and perceived stress, and these sex effects decreased when prior knowledge was controlled for, but remained significant. In the case of belonging uncertainty, prior knowledge increased the explained variance by about 5 % beyond sex, while in the case of stress about 2 % additional variance was explained. Thus, in line with Hypothesis 3, even when controlling for prior conceptual knowledge, female students still experienced higher belonging uncertainty and more stress than their male colleagues. Because of the presumably less important role of physics in the computer science first-year curriculum, we investigated whether findings regarding the predictive power of the bMCU would change when excluding the computer science students. This was not the case: when excluding these students from the analysis, the contribution of the bMCU measure in Step 2 remained $\beta = -0.18$ for belonging uncertainty, and changed only slightly, from $\beta = -0.12$ to $\beta = -0.14$, for perceived stress. The explained variance of the full model remained unchanged for both dependent variables.

3.2.3. Predicting academic success in first university year

The results of the hierarchical regression analysis for predicting first-year GPA are presented in Table 5. For ease of presentation, only standardized values are shown (unstandardized estimates are provided in Table S5 in the Supplementary Material).

Consistent with the descriptive data in Table 1, the effect of sex as a sole predictor of first-year GPA was significant, but very small (Table 5; Step 1). The sex effect favored males and explained 1 % of the variance in GPA. Including high school track and grades (Step 2a) improved GPA prediction significantly, although the sex effect was unchanged. Prior knowledge scores were significantly predictive of GPA beyond the

Table 2
Estimated correlations between study variables.

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Sex ^a	–									
2. HS track ^a	–0.13***	–								
3. HS GPA	0.07**	–0.08	–							
4. UY GPA	–0.10***	0.09**	0.52***	–						
5. bMCU	–0.31***	0.16***	0.27***	0.36***	–					
6. CCI	–0.18***	0.14***	0.39***	0.44***	0.49***	–				
7. Belonging	0.15***	–0.14***	–0.13***	–0.26***	–0.23***	–0.17***	–			
8. Perceived stress	0.23***	–0.06	–0.04	–0.25***	–0.20***	–0.14***	0.39***	–		
9. VEA	0.05	–0.04	0.17***	0.29***	–0.01	0.04	–0.11**	–0.25***	–	
10. VDA	0.01	–0.05	0.12**	0.16***	–0.02	–0.03	–0.12**	–0.21***	0.48***	–
11. VP	–0.01	0.02	0.17***	0.19***	0.02	0.06	–0.15***	–0.15***	0.42***	0.47***

Note. HS = high school; UY = university; bMCU = basic mechanics conceptual understanding; CCI = calculus concept inventory; VEA = volition: effort avoidance; VDA = volition: distraction avoidance; VP = volition: persistence.

***p < .001, **p < .01, *p < .05.

^a dummy coded so that higher values indicate “female” and “STEM track” respectively.

Table 3
Predicting bMCU and CCI by sex, school track and school grades.

bMCU									
Predictors	Step 1			Step 2			Step 3		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β
Sex ^a	–0.19***	0.02	–0.31	–0.19***	0.01	–0.31	–0.19***	0.02	–0.32
Track ^a				0.07***	0.01	0.15	0.07***	0.02	0.14
HS GPA				0.12***	0.01	0.30	0.12***	0.01	0.30
Sex*Track							0.01	0.04	0.01
R ²			0.10***			0.20***			0.20***

CCI									
Predictors	Step 1			Step 2			Step 3		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β
Sex ^a	–0.08***	0.01	–0.17	–0.08***	0.01	–0.18	–0.10***	0.02	–0.21
Track ^a				0.06***	0.01	0.16	0.05***	0.01	0.14
HS GPA				0.13***	0.01	0.41	0.13***	0.01	0.41
Sex*Track							0.02	0.03	0.04
R ²			0.03**			0.21***			0.21***

Note. HS = high school; GPA = grade point average; bMCU = basic mechanics conceptual understanding; CCI = calculus concept inventory.

*p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

^a dummy coded, higher values indicate “female” and “STEM track”, respectively.

effects of high school measures and sex, and their inclusion in the model reduced the sex effect to non-significance (Step 2b). Thus, higher conceptual knowledge in mathematics and physics at the beginning of the first bachelor year, as well as higher high-school grades and a STEM high-school track, predicted higher GPA at the end of the year regardless of sex. Interestingly, however, within the knowledge-achievement block, only prior knowledge eliminated the sex effect. Additionally, both socio-emotional factors and volitional self-regulation significantly predicted GPA beyond sex (Steps 3a and 3b). Even without considering prior knowledge and achievements, including these variables reduced the sex effect on GPA to non-significance. Notably, the socio-emotional factors block reduced the sex effect regardless of volitional regulation (additional analyses have shown that volitional regulation alone, in contrast, did not reduce the sex effect). Finally, when considering all variables in Step 4, the sex effect was substantially reduced and statistically non-significant, while each of the blocks (knowledge-achievements, negative experiences, and volitional regulation) independently contributed to the prediction of GPA. This comprehensive model explained the largest percentage of variance in GPA (43 %). Because of the presumably less important role of physics in the computer science first-year curriculum, we again investigated whether findings regarding the predictive power of the bMCU would change when excluding the

computer science students. This again was not the case: the contribution of the bMCU to first-year GPA increased only slightly, in Step 2b from $\beta = 0.13$ to $\beta = 0.14$, and in Step 4 from $\beta = 0.12$ to $\beta = 0.13$; the explained variance for the full model decreased slightly from 43 % to 41 %.

Summing up, in line with Hypothesis 4, we found that sex did not predict first-year GPA beyond the combined explanatory power of the other predictors. In fact, both the combination of prior knowledge and achievements, as well as the combination socio-emotional and volitional factors were sufficient to reduce the sex effect to non-significance on their own. In addition, results show that, regardless of sex, both prior conceptual knowledge and socio-emotional factors contributed significantly to GPA prediction beyond high-school grades and track.

3.3. Complementary analyses: Sex differences in prior knowledge vs. first-year GPA

Our results revealed that the sex difference in first-year GPA was substantially smaller than the differences found in prior conceptual math and physics knowledge at the beginning of the academic year, as visualized by the means and confidence intervals in Fig. 1. Exploratory, separate analyses for the five departments confirmed the picture: the size of sex differences in GPA never exceeded the size of the sex

Table 4
Predicting belonging uncertainty and perceived stress.

Belonging Uncertainty						
Predictors	Step 1			Step 2		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β
Sex ^a	0.75***	0.13	0.15	0.42**	0.14	0.08
bMCU				-1.44***	0.30	-0.18
CCI				-0.73	0.39	-0.07
R ²			0.02**			0.07***

Stress						
Predictors	Step 1			Step 2		
	B	SE B	β	B	SE B	β
Sex ^a	0.45***	0.06	0.24	0.35***	0.06	0.19
bMCU				-0.38**	0.14	-0.12
CCI				-0.28	0.18	-0.07
R ²			0.06***			0.08***

Note. bMCU = basic mechanics conceptual understanding; CCI = calculus concept inventory.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a dummy coded, higher values indicate “female”.

differences in bMCU or CCI.

Given that prior knowledge scores were strong predictors of first-year GPA, one could have expected larger GPA differences than those found. We therefore conducted additional analyses that addressed possible sources for this discrepancy.

First, we examined whether the initial sex differences in prior knowledge held also when excluding students who did not complete all exams (and hence had missing data on final GPA). These students might have differed from the rest in their initial prior knowledge. We found that sex differences in conceptual physics knowledge (bMCU) were highly similar for students who completed exams ($d = 0.84$) and those who did not ($d = 0.86$). The sex difference in calculus scores (CCI) tended to be smaller among students who completed exams ($d = 0.44$) compared with those who did not ($d = 0.60$), yet the former was still larger than the GPA difference ($d = 0.23$). Descriptive statistics for these subgroups are provided in Table S6a in the Supplementary Material. Thus, sex differences in prior knowledge scores, particularly in physics, were higher than the sex difference in first-year GPA even when limiting the analysis of prior knowledge to students who in fact attended the final exams.

Next, considering the prediction of first-year GPA reported in section 2.3.2, we tested for interaction effects between the main covariates and sex, which we assumed could have led to smaller sex differences in first-

year GPA. Specifically, if prior knowledge was a weaker predictor of first-year GPA in females than in males (sex X prior knowledge interaction), it would imply that female students employed effective strategies of catching up on lacks in prior knowledge to a stronger degree than male students, enabling them to obtain higher GPA than would be expected based on their prior knowledge. Similarly, if the effects of belonging uncertainty and stress on GPA were weaker among females than among males (sex X belonging; sex X stress interactions), it could mean that female students found better ways than male students to compensate for, or become less discouraged by, negative socio-emotional factors, eventually obtaining higher GPA than could be expected. Finally, if the effect of volitional regulation on GPA was stronger among females (sex X volition interaction), it could imply that female students relied more strongly than male students on volitional regulation of their learning, which in turn helped them obtain higher GPA than could be expected based on the other covariates. Testing these four interaction terms revealed that none of these effects were significant or of notable magnitude (the regression results are reported in Table S6b in the Supplementary Material). Thus, the effects of our main covariates on first-year GPA emerged as highly similar between sexes, indicating that the smaller sex difference in first-year GPA was not likely a result of differential effects of the covariates on first-year GPA.

4. Discussion

Based on extensive research on the underrepresentation of women in math-intensive fields, Ceci et al. (2014) concluded that most of the causes are to be found prior to university, particularly in students’ constrained and unconstrained choices. Our results show that even for students who have already made a choice in favor of math-intensive STEM fields, there are factors that may disadvantage women from the very beginning. Specifically, we found substantial sex differences favoring men on tests of conceptual knowledge in mathematics and physics, which were present despite females’ slightly better high school GPA, and even in the subsample of students who had attended a STEM track in high school. As physics was not part of the curriculum in computer science, knowledge in physics was not causally relevant for the first year GPA in this department. Nonetheless, entering the study program with high conceptual understanding in physics appeared to be positively predictive of the first-year exam grades across all departments. All in all, our findings raise concerns regarding an uneven start for males and females in terms of the relevant knowledge needed for succeeding in math-intensive STEM programs.

Our data further showed that women reported higher belonging uncertainty and higher stress during their first undergraduate year than men, and that these socio-emotional factors contributed to students’

Table 5
Hierarchical regression analysis for predicting first year GPA.

Predictors	Step 1	Step 2a	Step 2b	Step 3a	Step 3b	Step 4
	β	β	β	β	β	β
Sex ^a	-0.10***	-0.11***	-0.04	-0.01	-0.05	-0.02
HS track ^a		0.17***	0.08**			0.06*
HS GPA		0.58***	0.43***			0.37***
bMCU			0.13***			0.12***
CCI			0.19***			0.19***
Belonging				-0.21***	-0.21***	-0.08**
Stress				-0.22***	-0.11*	-0.09**
VEA					0.30***	0.18***
VDA					-0.06	0.01
VP					0.10	0.01
R ²	0.01*	0.34***	0.37***	0.13***	0.22***	0.43***

HS = high school; GPA = grade point average; bMCU = basic mechanics conceptual understanding; CCI = calculus concept inventory; VEA = volition: effort avoidance; VDA = volition: distraction avoidance; VP = volition: persistence.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

^a dummy coded, higher values indicate “female” and “STEM track” respectively.

Fig. 1. Standardized Estimated Means and 95 % CI for Conceptual Physics Knowledge (bMCU), Conceptual Mathematics Knowledge (CCI), and First Year GPA, Split by Sex.

success independently of prior knowledge. Thus, factors that typically emerge during university studies seem to keep playing a role for sex differences in achievements among STEM undergraduates. This aligns with previous findings on setbacks encountered by women in male-dominated study fields (Cheryan et al., 2017; Leslie et al., 2015; Walton et al., 2015). Our study adds to previous findings by simultaneously examining the role of preexisting and emerging factors during the first year at university among undergraduates in math-intensive STEM fields. In the following, we discuss the results and their implications in more detail.

4.1. Sex differences in prior conceptual knowledge

Our data shows that women performed less well on conceptual knowledge tests in mechanics and calculus at the time of entering university. Assuming that previous academic choices are relevant to this prior knowledge, we considered whether students came from ‘STEM’ or ‘non-STEM’ tracks in high school. Although the exact number of compulsory lessons varies between schools, students in STEM tracks receive more math and physics instruction than students in non-STEM tracks, which allows to cover more topics and to go deeper into the content. In line with this, we found that students from STEM tracks in high school showed better conceptual knowledge in physics and math than those who did not have a STEM focus in high school. However, in both types of tracks, men obtained higher scores than women on our math and physics conceptual knowledge tests. We also found uneven base rates of sex in school track, with 67 % of the male and only 51 % of the female students coming from STEM tracks. However, this asymmetry cannot fully account for the lower performance of females on prior knowledge tests, as males outperformed females to a similar degree when coming from STEM and non-STEM track. Thus, the lower prior knowledge scores obtained by women suggests that they did not gain equally well as men from instruction in advanced physics and mathematics in high school. This is an alarming hypothesis, especially given the fact that we studied young men and women who had actively chosen to enroll in a math-intensive STEM program. It would be important to know why, and under which conditions, men and women do not profit from high-school instruction to a similar extent. While our dataset, which does not contain any details on the extent, quality, or content of the instruction actually received in high school, does not allow us to further explore possible explanations, previous studies targeting high-

school samples have pointed to the relevance of instructional quality. For example, sex differences in high-school physics were found to be reduced by means of instruction that focused on conceptual understanding rather than computational procedures in a study by Hofer and colleagues (2018). The predictive power of the conceptual prior knowledge tests in math and physics on first-year university GPA in our sample also points towards the relevance of conceptual understanding for both male and female students. Further, math and physics might be particularly important parts of the high school curriculum when preparing students for a future career in math intensive STEM fields, independent of their sex (e.g., Kopparla, 2019).

4.2. Catching up: Compensation and cost

We found that, throughout their first year, women reported stronger belonging uncertainty and higher perceived stress than men. Prior knowledge in math and physics only partially reduced the sex effects on belonging uncertainty and perceived stress, i.e., given similar levels of prior knowledge, there were still significant differences on these variables. This implies that lower prior knowledge is not the only source for experiencing stress or belonging uncertainty. Other studies have shown that women might experience a “chilly climate” (e.g., Walton et al., 2015) in fields dominated by “masculine cultures” (Cheryan et al., 2017; Cheryan & Markus, 2020). Maybe these factors did play a role in our sample as well. There are evidence-based and relatively easy to implement interventions for mitigating belonging uncertainty and preventing a chilly climate (Kroeper et al., 2025). Universities should be informed about these interventions and encouraged to implement them.

With respect to first-year GPA, one important finding was that despite lower prior knowledge, and higher belonging uncertainty and perceived stress, women reached only slightly lower grades than men at the end of the first bachelor year. While the sex difference in first-year GPA is smaller than the one we found in prior knowledge, it still is both statistically significant and effectively relevant for the academic choices and chances of students.

Given that prior knowledge was an important predictor of first-year GPA, and given the sex differences in prior knowledge, one might have expected larger sex differences in first-year GPA than we observed. There could be various explanations for our finding, among them the possibility that compensation had taken place and enabled women to ‘catch up’ on knowledge, so that their grades almost match those of the

male students. While we cannot infer causal relations from the current data, we tested for several interaction effects that might suggest such processes. For example, relying more strongly on volition or being less vulnerable to negative effects of belonging uncertainty and stress might have facilitated learning and ‘catching up’. However, our analysis did not support such differential sex effects of volitional regulation, belonging uncertainty, or perceived stress on students’ first-year GPA. Of course, compensation might have occurred in other ways and involved factors not measured here. For example, the specific learning strategies women used throughout the semesters would likely have been relevant for any process of ‘catching up’. Furthermore, accounting for either pre-university knowledge and achievements, socio-emotional factors and self-regulation at university, or their combination, eliminated the mere effect of sex on first-year GPA in our statistical models. This shows that each of these factors, independently, is important for exploring possible indirect causes of sex differences in achievement in math-intensive STEM programs at university. Thus, it remains to be determined what helped female students compensate for prior knowledge gaps before reaching the first-year final exams phase. Future research could investigate whether students with initially lower prior knowledge, who are nevertheless achieving similar GPA as students with higher prior knowledge, have higher cognitive resources (e.g., cognitive abilities), are more motivated for and engaged with learning throughout the year, or use more appropriate learning strategies.

Finally, while the small sex differences in first-year GPA can be seen as a positive aspect of ‘catching up’, having to compensate for lower conceptual knowledge might also have contributed to women’s belonging uncertainty and stress, constituting a psychological cost of catching up. However, the sex differences in belonging uncertainty and stress could not be fully explained by differences in prior knowledge, indicating that they should not be attributed solely to the necessity of catching up on lacking conceptual knowledge. Rather, female students appear to encounter psychological costs that are at least partly due to their sex, rather than their prior knowledge.

4.3. Implications, limitations and future research directions: Beyond sex

While our study has yielded important insights into factors contributing to sex differences in math-intensive STEM programs, it also has some limitations. First, the design of our study did not allow us to draw causal inferences. Future studies should study the co-development of socio-emotional factors, self-regulation and learning gains at multiple time points, and analyze their subsequent effects on both academic achievements and students’ well-being. Second, we assessed students’ prior knowledge at the start of their first university year, and have very limited data on factors such as academic choices, extracurricular activities, instructional quality, or potential biases in teacher-learner interactions in high school that could explain the sex differences in prior math and physics knowledge we observed. Research on high school instruction in Mathematics and Physics has shown that a focus on conceptual understanding benefits male and female students alike (e.g., Hofer et al., 2018). Future studies could investigate whether students who underwent this kind of instruction have an advantage when studying a STEM subject at university. Third, we used first-year GPA as our main outcome measure, because it eventually decided about student retention and thus was the most relevant indicator of academic achievement. However, high-stakes exams like the end-of-first-year exams in our cohorts have been shown to inflate gender differences (e.g., Cai et al., 2019). Thus, the generalizability of our findings to contexts in which grades are based upon other assessment methods instead of, or in addition to, high-stakes exam scores may be limited. Fourth, several of our measures might need further validation. First of all, the prior knowledge tests showed moderate internal consistency, as is common for knowledge tests assessing a range of concepts (Stadler et al., 2021; Taber, 2018). Our approach to validation was to have the tests adapted from the U.S. version by two experienced mathematics educators, who

also elicited feedback on the tests and its items from subject matters experts from the participating departments in order to ensure the relevance of the concepts tested for students’ first-year curricula. Both tests showed correlations in the range between 0.25 and 0.38 with measures of aggregated academic achievement (high school GPA and first-year university GPA), as would be expectable (see Supplementary Material, Table S2). Nevertheless, it would be very valuable to have more specific data from alternative, subject-specific knowledge tests. While this would require additional, cohort-wide tests that were not feasible in the context of our study, repeated testing with a range of instruments might be an agenda for future research focusing on the development of conceptual knowledge during STEM students’ first semesters. Further, while students were not required to state their sex or gender on the test sheet in order to minimize potential stereotype threat (Spencer et al., 2016), we cannot exclude the possibility that the fact that students were asked consent for us to assess their registration information, including their sex, might still have induced stereotype threat at least in some participants. The belonging uncertainty scale had to be reduced to a two-item scale because the original three-item version had low internal consistency. Also, differences in reported belonging uncertainty might be partially explainable by gendered differences in the frequency and intensity to self-report emotions (cf. Brebner, 2003). Similarly, self-regulation was also obtained by self-report and thus may have been subject to systematic sex differences in self-reporting. Thus, to corroborate and expand our findings, further research employing a broader range of measures addressing social and emotional factors would be needed. Lastly, by relying on the official records to obtain information on students’ sex, we implemented a binary operationalization of gender (i.e., as sex assigned at birth) that may not always have been aligned with a person’s own gender identification. This approach follows the official academic reporting on diversity at ETH Zurich and the legislation in Switzerland, and it also aligns with previous research addressing the underrepresentation of women in STEM (e.g., Ceci et al., 2014; Cimpian et al., 2020; Stewart-Williams & Halsey, 2021). Nevertheless, a binary account of gender is problematic for many reasons (see Hyde et al., 2019, for an overview), and risks to overlook or misrepresent non-binary students. Research on diversity in STEM has much to gain from moving beyond a focus on female representation in STEM towards a broader discussion of factors determining pathways of so-far underrepresented groups into and within STEM, addressing aspects of sex and gender, race, family background and their intersections (e.g., French et al., 2023; Rainey et al., 2018). Future research could make use of multidimensional measures of gender identification to explore, for example, how degrees and types of gender identification interact with stereotype-driven effects on academic behaviors and outcomes (e.g., Schmader, 2002). On the other hand, we believe that many of our findings are relevant to all students, regardless of sex and gender. Even though our analyses relied heavily on sex differences in central tendencies, score distributions still highly overlapped between men and women. This means, for example, that low prior knowledge, high belonging uncertainty, and high perceived stress are prevalent among many students regardless of their sex, and impact their achievements. Thus, to support the academic success of incoming university students in math-intensive STEM fields, it will be helpful to create conditions in which students with low levels of relevant prior knowledge can catch up, in which measures are taken to help students keep stress to a tolerable level, and in which all students can develop a feeling of belonging, regardless of their minority status or the gender they identify with.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Anne Deiglmayr: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Michal Berkowitz:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Bruno Rüttsche:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Nora Dittmann:** Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Renate Schubert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision,

Conceptualization. **Elsbeth Stern**: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

none.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2025.102762>.

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